

samples 1 d before and after insecticide application. Each board was examined under a dissecting microscope.

Cypermethrin and cis-2-cypermethrin caused WBPH resurgence. Cis-2-cypermethrin caused BPH resurgence and hopperburn, and reduced yield 28% below that of the unsprayed control (Table 1). Carbofuran and BPMC gave

good control of both planthoppers.

When changes in populations of spiders, Coleoptera, mirid predators, and egg parasitoids were considered, the decline in spider populations was closely related to WBPH and BPH resurgence. Both pyrethroids were highly toxic to spiders, contributing to high hopper nymphspider ratios early in the period

of hopper population increase (Table 2).

Carbamates were less toxic to spiders and other natural enemies. Carbofuran and BPMC gave moderate or poor control of most other rice pests. Both pyrethroids gave excellent control of other rice pests and tested doses were not toxic to fish. *ℵ*

Gall midge (GM) activity and parasitization by *Platygaster oryzae* in Jaya stubble and wild rice at Bhubaneswar, India

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GM *Orseolia oryzae* (Wood-Mason) breeds in Jaya rice stubble during the off-season (Jan-Jun) and also in wild rice *Oryza perennis* (Moench). GM-infested tillers turn into silvershoots or galls which protrude from the leaf whorl (exposed galls). In unproductive and late formed tillers, many galls do not protrude from the leaf whorl and remain hidden in the culm (suppressed galls).

We studied GM abundance, activity, and parasitization due to *Platygaster oryzae* (Cameron) in Jaya rice stubble and in wild rice at OUAT in 1982.

Stubble was left in unsprayed fields planted to Jaya after harvesting the wet season crop (Jul-Dec). It was occasionally irrigated to encourage ratoon growth. Fields were divided into four quadrats and each quadrat into five subplots. From each subplot, one hill was uprooted at random at weekly intervals. In the laboratory, silvershoot infestation was recorded and the exposed and suppressed galls were dissected to determine parasitization. Twenty randomly selected hills of wild rice were collected weekly from swamps adjoining the Jaya fields and examined for midge attack and parasitization.

Gall midge was prevalent in Jaya stubble throughout the off-season, peaking at 17 wk (23-29 Apr). Parasitization peaked at 5 and 6 wk

Exposed and suppressed galls and parasitization of Jaya stubble and *O. perennis*, Bhubaneswar, India.

(29 Jan-11 Feb). Suppressed galls were maximum at 15 wk (9-15 Apr) (see figure).

O. perennis also harbored GM throughout the year, but infestation was lower than in stubble. Parasitization,

however, was higher. Gall occurrence was highest in the 3d (15-21 Jan) and 46th wk (12-18 Nov) and most galls were suppressed. GM infestation and parasitization followed a wax and wane cycle. *ℵ*

Stem injury in deep water rice as a guide for determining stem borer (SB) infestation at different growth stages

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SB *Scirpophaga incertulas* infestation generally is high in deep water rice. We

studied SB infestation at different internodes of deep water rice plants at harvest. Water level, plant height, stem elongation, internode formation, and growth phase were considered.

A 0.2-ha deep water field was planted to photoperiod-sensitive Jaladhi 1 in early Jun 1983. Soil was a clay loam with pH 7.0-7.5. At land preparation, 10 t farmyard manure/ha was applied. Standard cultivation methods were